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Application of high-performance liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry with a quadrupole/linear ion trap instrument for the analysis of pesticide residues in olive oil

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the development of an enhanced liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC–MS) method for the analysis of pesticides in olive oil. One hundred pesticides belonging to different classes and that are currently used in agriculture have been included in this method. The LC–MS method was developed using a hybrid quadrupole/linear ion trap (QqQ_{LIT}) analyzer. Key features of this technique are the rapid scan acquisition times, high specificity and high sensitivity it enables when the multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode or the linear ion-trap operational mode is employed. The application of 5 ms dwell times using a linearly accelerating (LINAC) high-pressure collision cell enabled the analysis of a high number of pesticides, with enough data points acquired for optimal peak definition in MRM operation mode and for satisfactory quantitative determinations to be made. The method quantifies over a linear dynamic range of LOQs (0.03–10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) up to 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Matrix effects were evaluated by comparing the slopes of matrix-matched and solvent-based calibration curves. Weak suppression or enhancement of signals was observed (<15% for most—80—of the pesticides). A study to assess the identification criteria based on the MRM ratio was carried out by comparing the variations observed in standard vs matrix (in terms of coefficient of variation, CV%) and within the linear range of concentrations studied. The CV was lower than 15% when the response observed in solvent was compared to that in olive oil. The limit of detection was $\leq 10 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for five of the selected pesticides, $\leq 5 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for 14, and $\leq 1 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for 81 pesticides. For pesticides where additional structural information was necessary for confirmatory purposes—in particular at low concentrations, since the second transition could not be detected—survey scans for enhanced product ion (EPI) and MS3 were developed.

Keywords: Pesticide residues; Olive oil; QTRAP analyzer; Quantitation; Matrix effects

Introduction

Olive oil is an important commodity in the Mediterranean Basin. “Virgin olive oil” is obtained from the fruit of the olive tree (*Olea Europaea*), exclusively by mechanical and/ or physical means without any subsequent treatment. Over the past few decades, knowledge gained about the nutritional health benefits of this oil has increased the demand for this product worldwide [1].

The control of diseases and pests in olive trees is a critical factor that increases the number and/or size of olives, and thus the resulting yield. In agricultural practice for olive groves, the use of insecticides and herbicides provides an unquestionable benefit for crop protection. However, these pesticide residues can persist up to the harvest stage, making the contamination of the olives used to produce olive oil possible [2].

Several countries as well as the European Union (EU) and the Codex Alimentarius Commission—part of the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the World Health Organization (WHO)—have established maximum residue limits (MRLs) in both olives and olive oil that cover a large number of pesticides [3–5]. The monitoring of pesticide residues in olive oil is therefore crucial to ensuring food safety and compliance with pesticide MRLs. For this purpose, the development of multiresidue methods which allow the proper control of a large number of pesticides in each analysis (injection) is the most common strategy. Because of this, it is important for pesticide residue analysis laboratories to be able to cover and detect other pesticides, not just those registered in their country.

Pesticide residue determination in olive oil is a very demanding task considering the inherent complexity of the matrix due to its high fat content. Methods applied to determine pesticide residues in fatty food often require a lot of steps and are very time-consuming. Also, the different classes and physicochemical properties involved make it difficult to develop methodologies that cover all of the analytes under study. The procedure normally includes three steps: extraction, cleanup and chromatographic determination. Of these three, cleanup is the most laborious but it is the key to the whole process, since small amounts of coextracted lipids can harm the chromatographic system and cause signal suppression. Pesticide extraction is also a critical point, and different methods are used to isolate pesticides from fat. Different sample treatment procedures have been proposed for the analysis of pesticides in olive oil [6]. The most common extraction technique used was liquid–liquid extraction (LLE) of pesticides from the oil, followed by a liquid or solid-phase extraction (SPE) cleanup [7–11]. Cleanup with gel permeation chromatography (GPC) [12–14], solid-phase microextraction (SPME) [15], matrix solid-phase dispersion (MSPD) [16] and direct on-line reversed-phase liquid chromatography–GC analysis (RPLC–GC) [17] have

also been effectively developed. Recently, the use of QuEChERS sample preparation has been validated and applied with success to fatty matrices, including olive oil and avocado [18, 19].

To date, GC-MS and GC-MS² have been the techniques of choice for pesticide residue analysis in olive oil. However, the number of newly authorized pesticides and commercial formulations used in olive groves increases each year—in line with integrated pest-management guidelines—and the tendency to apply these new polar compounds has prompted the use of LC-MS as a complementary tool to GC-MS, particularly for compounds not amenable to GC. In this new scenario, the use of LC-MS will be mandatory in future.

However, hardly any literature is available on the analysis of pesticides residues in olive oil by liquid chromatography/ mass spectrometry [16, 19–22]. Barrek et al. proposed the first method that used a single quadrupole analyzer in SIM mode to attain typical LODs of 40–200 µg kg⁻¹ [22]. An LC/ion trap-MS/MS method was developed for four triazines and dimethoate [16], and more recently a triple quadrupole method was developed for eight multiclass pesticides [19] and for two quaternary ammonium herbicides using LC/MS/MS in SRM mode [21]. The use of LC/ TOFMS for the analysis of herbicides in olive oil was also proposed recently [20].

Recently, hybrid triple quadrupole linear ion trap instruments (QTRAP, Applied Biosystems, Concord, ON, Canada) have been introduced and applied to quantitative small molecule screening with very fast trap scan speeds [23–26] (up to 4000 amu/s), which makes simultaneous and multiple MS/MS experiments feasible. These instruments also offer the possibility of collecting structural information (product ions spectra) triggered by information-dependent acquisition (IDA) survey scans, such as SRM; precursor (prec); neutral loss (NL) and Q3 multiple ion. Of these surveys, SRM represents the most selective, specific and sensitive mode for triple quadrupole instruments.

The objective of this work was the development of a multiresidue method for the determination of 100 multiclass pesticides in olive oil—including those most commonly used in olive groves in Mediterranean countries—using a hybrid triple quadrupole linear ion trap mass spectrometer (QTRAP). Identification and confirmation of target compounds by electrospray tandem mass spectrometry was based on two MS/MS transitions [multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode]. The pesticides were extracted from the fatty matrix using a liquid-liquid partition step followed by a dispersive solid-phase extraction (SPE) cleanup step, using PSA, C₁₈ and GCB. The method is very sensitive and the first LC-MS/MS of its kind developed for a large number of pesticides in olive oil (>50). This is the first report on the application of LC/QqLIT to pesticide residue analysis in fatty matrices. Several analytical parameters—the sensitivity, linearity, precision, matrix effects and limits of detection (LODs)—have been carefully evaluated.

Experimental

Pesticide standards and reagents

The group of 100 pesticides includes organophosphates, *N*-methylcarbamates, benzimidazoles, azoles, ureas, benzoylphenylureas, carboxylic acids, triazines, uracils, chloroacetamides, triazols and ketoenoles. Table 1 shows the selected pesticides. Pesticide standards of analytical grade were supplied by Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Augsburg, Germany) or Riedel-de-Haën (Selze, Germany). Stock standard solutions of single pesticides were prepared in methanol at a concentration of 5 mg/ml. A working standard solution was prepared from standard mixture solutions of groups of pesticides stored at -20 °C.

HPLC-grade acetonitrile was purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Formic acid (98% purity) was supplied by Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). Water used for LC-MS analysis was generated from a Millipore Milli-Q Plus Ultra Pure Water System (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA) with a specific resistance of >18 MO.

Sample treatment

The procedure employed is similar to the so-called "QhEChERS" described elsewhere [19], comprising the following steps: a representative 3-g portion of previously homogenized sample was weighed in a 50 ml PTFE centrifuge tube with 7 g of water. This procedure offers advantageous features for the analyses of polar pesticides. It is an extraction method with less labor-intensive sample preparation steps and it is less time-consuming. Then 10 ml of acetonitrile were added, along with 1 g of NaCl and 4 g of anhydrous MgSO₄, and it was shaken vigorously for 1 min. The NaCl and MgSO₄ were purchased from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain) and Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), respectively. The extract was then centrifuged (3700 rpm) for 4 min. For the clean-up step, 5 ml of the supernatant (acetonitrile phase) was withdrawn using a pipette and transferred to a 15-ml PTFE centrifuge tube containing 250 mg of primary secondary amine (PSA) sorbent, 750 mg of anhydrous MgSO₄, 250 mg of C₁₈ and 250 mg of graphitized carbon black (GCB). It was then energetically shaken for 20 s. PSA and C18 packs were from Varian (Harbor City, CA, USA) and GCB was from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA). The extract was centrifuged again (3700 rpm) for 4 min. Finally, a 1-mL aliquot of the extract was evaporated with a gentle stream of nitrogen until nearly dry and then reconstituted to a final volume of 0.3 mL of the same organic solvent content as that of the initial mobile phase (10% MeOH) so that the extract contained the equivalent of 1 g of

sample per ml. Prior to LC/MS analysis the extract was filtered through a 0.45 µm PTFE filter (Millex FG, Millipore). The recoveries obtained using this procedure were satisfactory, except for the less polar pesticides—such as organochlorines—which had recovery rates below 70% [27].

LC-MS analysis

An Agilent 1100 HPLC system equipped with binary pumps was used for LC analyses. Different LC conditions were evaluated by making use of two chromatographic columns, different working flows and different injection volumes, in an approach intended to achieve optimum sensitivity. The columns selected for this study were C8 with different characteristics (100×2.1 mm i.d., 1.8 µm particle size and 150×4.6 mm, 5 µm particle size) from Agilent Technologies (Palo Alto, CA, USA). The mobile phases used in both columns were HPLC water, 0.1% formic acid (mobile phase B) and acetonitrile (mobile phase A). The LC gradient started with 40% of A and was linearly increased to 100% A over 30 min. Flow rates of 200 and 600 µl/min were explored in the C18 column (150×4.6 mm i.d.). The maximum flow rate for this column (1000 µl/min) was not tested. The flow rate assayed using a 100×2.1 mm i.d. column was the maximum recommendable for this column (200 µl/min).

Mass spectrometric analyses were carried out using a 3200 QTRAP MS/MS system (Applied Biosystems). The QTRAP analyzer is a system that combines a fully functional triple quadrupole and ion-trap mass spectrometer within the same platform. The collision cell (Q2) incorporates a system of linear acceleration (LINAC) of ions through the quadrupole, providing faster MS/MS scanning (reduced dwell times) without sensitivity losses and making the analysis of a large number of MRM transitions possible (~240 per segment of the MS run). Another advantage is that LINAC makes use of a field gradient to accelerate the fragment ions towards Q3 and so avoids “cross-talk” phenomena [28].

Optimization of the MS parameters was achieved by performing flow injection analysis (FIA) for each compound. Table 1 shows the values of the instrumental settings optimized: declustering potential (DP); entrance potential (EP); collision cell entrance potential (CEP) for precursor ions and collision energy (CE); and collision cell exit potential (CXP) for product ions. The analyses were performed using a turboionspray source in positive mode. The operation conditions were as follows: ionspray voltage, 5000 V; curtain gas, 20 (arbitrary units); nebulizer gas 1 and auxiliary gas 2 (GS1 and GS2) of 50 and 40, respectively; the probe temperature was 400 °C. Nitrogen served as the turbo gas and the collision gas. Mass calibration and resolution adjustments on the resolving quadrupoles were performed automatically using a 10–5 mol/l solution of poly(propylene glycol)

introduced via a syringe pump and connected to the interface. MRM experiments were carried out to obtain the maximum sensitivity for the detection of the selected pesticides. Additional experiments were developed for four pesticides where further structural information was necessary for confirmatory purposes. In these cases, the QTRAP system operated in enhanced product ion (EPI) mode and MS3 mode. The additional compound-dependent parameters optimized were: CES (collision energy spread) at 10 (arbitrary units) and AF2 (excitation energy) at values ranging from 10 to 20 V. Table 1 also shows the MRM transitions used for the confirmation and quantification of pesticides. The confirmation of pesticides was performed by means of two MRM transitions and by monitoring the MRM ratio. The most intense MRM transition was selected for quantitation purposes. Applied Biosystem/MDS SCIEX Analyst software was used for data acquisition and processing.

Validation study

The qualitative analysis of pesticide residues in food commodities using a triple quadrupole analyzer is commonly performed for confirmatory purposes, based on the criteria of retention time, MRM transitions and MRM ratio. When the MRM method is performed with LINAC technology, the advantage is a short analytical turn-around time without any loss of analytical quality or reliability. However, when a broad range of analytes have to be covered in a single analysis, a possible limitation on qualitative analysis could be the fact that some pesticides and matrix interferences might have common MRM transitions, making the confirmation of pesticides in food samples difficult. As a result, the MRM ratio cannot appear within an acceptable confidence interval between the standard in solvents and the samples. Possible causes of this can be, for instance, when one mass transition overlaps a coeluting matrix compound or another coeluting analyte. In these cases, the use of confirmation criteria based on the MRM ratio can avoid the detection of positive findings in food samples. This key parameter is also crucial to the quantitative determination, since the MRM ratio is the peak area ratio of MRM transitions (quantifier and qualifier mass transitions). Because of this, a validation study has been developed to evaluate the variation (in terms of CV%) in the MRM parameter ratio between the standard and the matrix and over a range of concentrations (from LOQs to 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) for its application for qualitative and quantitative purposes. The corresponding analyses were performed in triplicate to obtain this data.

Sensitivity determination of the analytical method as well as quantitative evaluations were also objectives of this validation study. The limit of detection (LOD) of the target pesticides was experimentally determined as the minimum concentration of analyte which

gives a signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio of 3. The criteria for the experimental determination of limit of quantification (LOQ) was established for a S/N ratio of 10. LODs and LOQs were determined by analyzing spiked extracts of olive oil (six replicates were analyzed). For quantitative analysis and the assessment of matrix effects, matrix-matched samples were prepared for external calibration. Linearity was tested by assessing signal responses of target analytes in the standard and in the matrix over a range of concentrations from the LOQs up to 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. The analyses were performed in triplicate. Matrix effects were evaluated by comparing the slopes calculated from the calibration curves prepared in solvent to those obtained in the matrix. To prepare matrix-matched calibrators, extracts of blank matrix were dried with a stream of nitrogen and spiked with standard solutions at comparable concentrations to those used for the solvent- based calibrators. In this study, one type of olive oil was used. Enhancement or suppression of signal was calculated as the quotient of the slopes in the solvent and the matrix, and was expressed as a percentage.

Intraday and interday variabilities were determined by the repeated analysis ($n = 5$) of spiked samples of olive oil at 1, 5 and 20 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, from run-to-run over one day and five days, respectively.

Results and discussion

LC analysis

To achieve sufficient sensitivity for the detection of pesticides in olive oil, different LC conditions were assayed, as was discussed in the previous section. Multiresidue methods are always a compromise and given the variety of pesticides included for this method, the composition of the mobile phase chosen was water, 0.1% formic acid and ACN. One approach applied to improve sensitivity was the use of small particle size (e.g., 1.8 μm) columns, which can provide an increased column efficiency with better baseline separation and narrower peaks than standard particle size columns (e.g., 3.5–5 μm). These were the results observed in our analyses, but, on the other hand, the sensitivity achieved in small particle size columns is limited by the volume of sample that can be injected. In high-demand conditions, small particle size columns, such as 2.1 \times 100 mm, could even support the injection of higher volumes (e.g., 10 μL) than the maximum recommended (5 μL) without significant changes in the column pressure. However, the disadvantage of this is a worsening of the peak shape. After comparing both columns, and using a mobile phase of water, 0.1% formic acid and ACN, the 4.6 \times 150 mm column was chosen, at 5 μm , with an injection volume of 10 μL . A weaker

solvent was not tried in the composition of the mobile phase when using a 2.1× 100 mm column, in order to test a possible improvement in peak shape when a higher volume of sample is injected, exceeding the maximum recommended.

Another option assayed with a view to optimizing the sensitivity was the flow rate when using a 4.6×150 mm column. The capacity of the turboionspray source allowed us to operate at maximum flow rates of 800–1000 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. For fast separations, which are needed to reduce analysis times in LC instruments, monolithic silica columns can also operate at high flow rates while maintaining both a high sample loading capacity and good chromatographic resolution [29, 30]. Upon exploring two flow rates—200 and 600 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ —in term of sensitivity, a superior response was observed at 200 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, and so this was judged to be more suited to the trace determination of pesticides. The benefit of using higher flow rates is a reduction in analysis time, which is ideal for routine laboratory analysis. However, reduced sensitivity was observed at the higher flow rate explored, which could be associated with a dilution effect or a less stable spray.

Taking into account the results obtained by comparing the LC conditions assayed, one can conclude that noticeable differences in term of sensitivity were observed. Figure 1 presents the results obtained from the LC conditions assayed. Using the 2.1×100 mm column with a 1.8 μm particle size, 64 of the pesticides selected, could be determined at LODs equal to or below 1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, while 81 pesticides could be detected at this level when using the 4.6×150 mm column, with a 5 μm particle size. The LODs for the other pesticides were equal to or lower than 5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (14 pesticides) and 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (5 pesticides). Table 2 presents the LODs for olive oil extracts obtained using the 4.6×150 mm column, with a 5 μm particle size.

Qualitative evaluation of the MS data

Triple quadrupole or QTRAP systems working in MRM operation mode yield a high selectivity, which is well-suited to multiresidue methods. However, when the multiresidue method includes a wide range of analytes and the matrix sample is complex, additional analyzer features can be crucial to the success of the analytical method. The presence of matrix or analyte interference can prove problematic when interpreting the analytical results. Among the pesticides included during the development of the multiresidue method, diuron and flumeturon serve as examples that illustrate the effectiveness of applying analytical techniques that provide enhanced resolution and that permit the detection of masses with differences of 0.15 amu. Therefore, and in spite of the fact that diuron and

fluometuron are not coeluting analytes (their retention times are 17.01 and 17.55, respectively), both analytes have the same MRM transition (233→72). In triple quadrupole systems with one unit of mass resolution, one of these analytes can appear as interference, while diuron and fluometuron are resolved (233.1→72.1, 233.2→72.1, respectively) when using the QTRAP analyzer. Figure 2 shows a MRM chromatogram corresponding to the detection of diuron and fluometuron.

The best sensitivity in MRM operation mode was achieved through the acquisition of MRM transitions at a dwell time of 5 ms for each mass transition (the total number of MRM transitions was 202 and the pause time between scan cycles was 4 ms). The acquisition was performed in just one segment of the analysis, obtaining sufficient scans for each peak. The maximum number of MRM transitions that can be acquired per segment is 240. Figure 3 shows an extracted ion chromatogram (EIC), corresponding to 202 MRM transitions obtained at a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Satisfactory performance for quantitative analysis was still achieved when reduced dwell times (5 ms) were used, even though this affects the S/N ratio and peak area.

Another criterion used to distinguish an analyte from coeluting analytes or matrix interferences was the MRM ratio. The use of this parameter can also be also effective when the fragmentation of a molecule does not provide more than two MRM transitions. On the other hand, the use of the MRM ratio as an identification criterion is possible when the relative transition intensity corresponds to that of the calibration standard from either calibration solutions or from spiked samples at comparable concentrations. A maximum permitted tolerance for relative ion intensities, when using LC-MS techniques, is also indicated in regulatory guidelines concerning the interpretation of results [31]. Taking the tolerance range indicated in these guidelines as a reference for LC-MS techniques (from 20 to 50%), a lower tolerance value of 15% could also be considered to be admissible. Because of this, MRM ratios have been calculated for pesticide standard solutions and matrix. Table 3 summarizes the MRM ratios calculated in solvent and matrix, corresponding to the mean values obtained for a range of concentration from LOQ up to 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Also included in the table are the CVs of the MRM ratio within this range of concentrations (expressed in percentage), the difference between the MRM ratios in the solvent and the matrix, and the difference between the CVs calculated.

As shown in Table 3, the CVs obtained for the pesticides studied indicate optimal system performance. This means that variations observed when comparing MRM ratios at low and high concentrations of pesticide standard, as well as the responses in matrix and solvent, were within an acceptable confidence interval. For all of the pesticides selected, the differences between the MRM ratios in solvent and matrix, within the range of

concentrations evaluated, were lower than 15%. Based on these results, it can be deduced that the MRM ratio parameter can be used as a key criterion for identification and also for further quantitative analysis.

The use of the MRM ratio is limited, however, at low analyte concentrations where the second MRM transition is not detected due to a large difference between both MRM transitions. This is the case with the pesticides spinosyn A, spinosyn D, miconazole and vinclozolina, whose MRM ratios are within the range 20–30. An alternative to the QTRAP system is to use information-dependent acquisition (IDA) to trigger additional survey scans. In this way, it is feasible to combine a survey scan acquired in MRM operation mode (triple quadrupole) with another survey scan in EPI mode or in MS3 mode (linear ion trap, LIT)—all in a single run. Thus, one MRM transition could be used for quantification, and the structural information obtained with MS2 (using the EPI mode or the MS3 scan mode) could be used to confirm the identities of the analytes. Using this approach, the number of compounds analyzed could be doubled when a MRM survey scan is combined with an EPI scan in an MS run. For instance, approximately 240 MRM transitions could be acquired as quantifier mass transitions, while the EPI mode could be used for confirmatory purposes. On the other hand, improved sensitivity could be achieved given the ion accumulation capacity of the linear trap, with an ion path that is 20× longer than a three-dimensional ion trap analyzer. Taking this alternative into account, an additional method was developed for spinosyn D, spinosyn A, miconazole and vinclozolina, where the MRM mode was combined with survey scans (EPI and MS3) via IDA. For miconazole and spinosyn A, the structural information obtained using the EPI mode was not sufficient for confirmatory purposes. An additional survey scan in MS3 was necessary to provide further structural information. This was because the abundance of the fragment ions obtained in EPI mode was similar to that obtained using MRM mode. The spectra obtained in EPI mode for spinosyn A show two fragment ions (at m/z 142 and 98) as a result of the fragmentation of the precursor ion (at m/z 732). However, the intensity of the fragment ion at m/z 98 is ~10%, and the tolerance range used for relative ion intensities is based on regulatory guidelines, this could be a limitation [31] for confirmatory purposes. The fragment ion at m/z 142.2 observed in the MS3 survey scan for spinosyn A provided another abundant fragment ion at m/z 98.0, making it possible to use this structural information for its confirmation. An additional MS3 survey scan was also appropriate for the analysis of miconazole, since the fragmentation of the precursor ion at m/z 415 provided two fragment ions at m/z 159 and 123. However, the intensity of m/z 123 is also ~10% compared to the most intense ion (m/z 159). Figures 4 and 5 show survey scans acquired in the MRM, EPI and MS3 modes for spinosyn A and miconazole, respectively. One useful feature of the QTRAP analyzer is its ion accumulation

capacity, which is higher than a conventional three-dimensional ion trap analyzer. This means that the QTRAP analyzer can provide improved sensitivity. The sensitivities achieved when using the MRM and EPI modes were similar for both spinosyn D and miconazole. On the other hand, the confirmation could be supported by further structural information. This feature is advantageous, since a high number of analytes can be analyzed using a combination of MRM and EPI or MS3 survey scans.

Quantitative evaluation and matrix effect assessment

The linear equations for the matrix-matched and the solvent- based standard calibration curves are shown in Table 2. The ratio of the slopes of the corresponding calibration curves can be used to investigate the influence of the matrix on the signal response. If this ratio is about 1, no matrix effect is observed. If the slope of the matrix-matched calibration curve is smaller or larger than the solvent standard calibration curve—indicating an enhancing or suppressing effect of the matrix—then this can influence the quantitative analysis. The matrix effect can also be presented as a percentage to show the size of the difference between the slopes of the corresponding calibration curves and the degree of enhancement or suppression in the signal response (see Table 2).

For most of the pesticides studied (91), a weak matrix effect equal to or lower than 20% was observed. Among these, the matrix effect was equal to or lower than 10% for 66 pesticides, and approximately half of these pesticides exhibited signal enhancement while the other half exhibited signal suppression. The pesticides fluometuron, difenoxuron, diuron, malathion, spynosin D and spynosin A all showed a higher degree of signal suppression (in the range of 22–27%), while only cyromazine exhibited a strong signal suppression effect (45%). Ethoxiquin and hexaflumuron showed relatively strong signal enhancement effects (~34–35%).

From these results, it is clear that the matrix effect observed was tolerable (10–20%) for most of the pesticides, while it was stronger for nine pesticides. One option to minimize matrix effects is to dilute the samples in order to reduce the presence of matrix interference. This option is widely accepted, since it is easy to apply and reliable, in particular for routine laboratory analysis [32, 33]. The correlation coefficients of both calibration curves were higher than 0.997 (see Table 2).

LOQs calculated in the matrix are also presented in Table 2. The method has demonstrated enough sensitivity to be applied to the quantitative analysis of trace pesticides in food. Approximately 50% of the pesticides have LOQs that are equal or lower than 1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, 35% of them are equal to or lower than 5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, 6% of them are equal to or lower than 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$.

kg⁻¹, and 8% of them have LOQs between 15 and 20 µg kg⁻¹. The precision of the method, as evaluated by determining the inter- and intraday variabilities, was acceptable. The precision calculated as the relative standard deviation, RSD, was lower than 15% for the three concentrations tested (1, 5 and 20 µg kg⁻¹). Data related to the precision are not presented in the tables.

Conclusions

Using the hybrid quadrupole/linear ion trap (QqQ_{LIT}), an LC-MS method of analysis was developed for the multi-residue determination of pesticides in olive oil, that operated at fast scan acquisition times in MRM mode. The application of reduced dwell times (5 ms) enabled the analysis of one hundred pesticides in just one segment of analysis time, which yielded enough acquisition data points to achieve optimal peak definition and satisfactory quantitative determinations. The MRM ratio can provide a key parameter during qualitative evaluations, especially when coeluting analytes or matrix interferences are present during multiresidue analysis. For pesticides whose second MRM transition cannot be detected at low concentrations, the alternative was to use a combination of MRM, EPI and MS3 survey scans and IDA. The MRM ratios of the selected pesticides, evaluated within the concentration range for LOQs up to 500 µg kg⁻¹, and obtained in solvent and in matrix, were within an acceptable confidence interval (<15%). For quantitative evaluation, matrix effects were evaluated by comparing the slopes of the matrix-matched and solvent-based calibration curves. The matrix effects displayed by most of the pesticides (80) were weak (<15%). Dilution of the sample extract is an easy and reliable method that can be used to minimize any matrix effects. The sensitivity of the LC-MS method is sufficient for it to be applicable to the determination of pesticide residues in olive oil. The LODs obtained using the method were ≤1 µg kg⁻¹ for 84 pesticides, ≤5 µg kg⁻¹ for 12, and ≤10 µg kg⁻¹ for four of the selected pesticides.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge funding support from Junta de Andalusia (Regional Government of Andalusia (Spain) (Research Groups FQM 323, AGR 159, Project FQM-01463), the Spanish “Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia” (Project BQU-2006- 15066) and The European Commission, GD SANCO (Specific Agreement No 2006/1 to the Framework Partnership Agreement No. SANCO/2006/FOOD SAFETY/025—Pesticides in Fruit and Vegetables). The authors wish to acknowledge Applied Biosystems, whose instrumentation facilities and

technical support made the development of this study possible. M.D. Hernando also acknowledges the research contract “Contrato de Retorno de Investigadores” from Consejería de Educación y Ciencia de la Junta de Andalucía, Spain.

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Fig. 1 LC conditions assayed using columns with different particle sizes, flow rates and injection volumes

Fig. 2 MRM chromatogram corresponding to the detection of diuron and fluometuron via the QTRAP system, using a mass resolution of 0.15 amu

Fig. 3 Extracted ion chromatogram corresponding to 202 MRM transitions at a concentration of $10 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for an extract of olive oil

Fig. 4 Combination of MRM, EPI and MS3 survey scans used in IDA to confirm the identity of spinosyn A

Fig. 5 Combination of MRM, EPI and MS3 survey scans used in IDA to confirm the identity of miconazole

Table 1. Operational MRM conditions and MRM transitions used for the quantitation and confirmation of pesticides

Values of MS parameters								
Pesticide	RT (min)	Quantitation MRM1	Confirmation MRM2	DP (V)	EP (V)	CEP (V)	CE (MRM1, MRM2) (V)	CXP (MRM1, MRM2)
Cyromazine	2.2	167.0/85.1	167.0/108.1	37	5	14.90	(24, 28)	(2,2)
Thiocyclam	3.7	182.2/137.1	182.2/73.1	45	5	15.33	(20, 34)	(1.3, 1.6)
Nitempyram	3.8	271.2/225.1	271.2/99.1	51	4	17.82	(14,20)	(3,1)
Aldicarb sulfoxide	3.8	207.1/132.0	207.1/89.1	34	5	16.03	(21, 8)	(2,2)
Carbendazim	3.8	192.4/160.2	192.4/132.1	52	5	15.61	(24,42)	(3,2)
Thiabendazole	3.8	202.0/131.2	202.0/175.2	59	5	15.88	(35,42)	(2,2)
Monocrotophos	3.8	224.1/127.0	224.1/98.1	42	5	16.50	(22,15)	(2.5,2)
Butoxycarboxin	4.7	223.1/106.2	223.1/63.0	35	6	16.47	(10,16)	(1,1)
Oxamyl	4.7	220.1/72.2	220.1/90.1	37	6	16.39	(11,21)	(1,1)
Cambendazole	4.7	303.1/217.3	303.1/261.2	66	7	18.71	(38,22)	(3,4)
Aldicarb sulfone	5.2	223.2/148.1	223.2/86.0	45	4	16.48	(12,20)	(3,2)
Methiocarb sulfoxide	6.2	242.2/185.2	242.2/170.2	42	5	17.01	(16,32)	(3,3)
Thiametoxam	6.5	292.2/211.2	292.2/132.1	41	3	18.41	(18,24)	(3,2)
Methomyl	6.5	163.3/106.1	163.3/88.1	20	5	14.80	(14,14)	(1.8, 1.8)
Oxfendazole	7.5	316.2/159.1	316.2/191.1	63	4	19.08	(41,26)	(2,2)
Metamitron	8.8	203.1/175.3	203.1/104.1	42	4	15.91	(27,23)	(1,2)
Chloridazon	10.0	222.0/92.0	222.0/77.0	60	3	16.44	(47,38)	(1,1)
Imidacloprid	10.3	256.3/209.2	256.3/175.1	56	5	17.40	(24,26)	(2.5,2)
Fenuron	10.4	166.0/72.2	166.0/109.2	30	5	14.88	(15,14.8)	(2,2)
Acetamiprid	11.01	223.2/126.2	223.2/56.1	50	5	16.48	(27.5, 31)	(2,2)
Dimethoate	11.3	230.1/125.1	230.1/199.2	38	2.6	16.67	(27,14)	(2.2,2.9)
Imazalil	11.8	297.1/159.1	297.1/109.2	20	5	18.55	(28, 26)	(2, 2.5)
Albendazole	11.3	266.2/234.1	266.2/191.2	64	6	17.68	(26,46)	(2,4)
Methiocarb sulfone	12.6	258.2/122.1	258.2/201.1	44	5	17.46	(24,11)	(2,3)
Mebendazole	12.9	296.2/264.3	296.2/105.3	52	8	18.52	(26,45)	(3,2)
Cymoxanil	13.1	199.1/111.0	199.1/128.2	32	4	15.80	(12,23)	(3,2)
Thiacloprid	13.2	253.2/126.1	253.2/99.0	52	5	17.32	(27.5, 56)	(2,2)
Butocarboxin	13.4	213.2/75.0	213.2/156.0	77	6	16.20	(18,12)	(1,3)
Spiroxamine	13.8	298.0/144.3	298.0/100.0	43	8	18.57	(29,43)	(2,1)
Aldicarb	14.2	213.2/89.1	213.2/116.2	30	5	16.20	(22,15.8)	(2,2)
Oxadixyl	14.2	279.2/219.2	279.2/102.1	54	4	18.04	(13,12)	(2,2)
Bromacil	14.2	261.2/205.0	261.2/187.9	32	7	17.54	(20,34)	(3,2)
Spinosyn A	14.5	732.7/142.2	732.7/189.3	20	5	30.74	(40,42)	(2,2)
Monuron	14.6	199.2/72.2	199.2/126.1	26	5	15.80	(32,34)	(2,2)
Lenacil	14.8	235.2/153.3	235.2/136.3	33	5	16.81	(25,43)	(2,2)
Simazine	14.9	202.1/132.2	202.1/124.2	50	5	15.89	(23,25)	(1.7, 1.79)
Miconazole	15.0	415.1/159.1	415.1/227.2	40	6	21.85	(40,26)	(2,2)
Spinosyn D	15.2	746.5/142.2	746.5/189.2	20	5	31.13	(46,40)	(2,2)
Desethylterbutylazine	15.2	202.1/146.1	202.1/104.0	36	5	15.89	(20,40)	(2,1.5)
Fenbendazole	15.5	300.0/268.2	300.0/159.3	55	4	18.63	(25, 46)	(2,2)
Metolcarb	15.6	166.1/109.2	166.1/94.1	27	5	14.88	(16,40)	(2,2)
Pyrimethanil	16.9	200.3/77.0	200.3/67.0	45	5	15.84	(55,58)	(1,1)
Prometryn	16.2	242.3/158.2	242.3/200.2	18	5	17.01	(22,33)	(3,3)
Terbutrin	16.4	242.2/186.2	242.2/71.2	57	5	17.01	(24,47)	(2,2)
Ethoxyquin	16.5	218.3/174.3	218.3/188.2	69	7	16.34	(40,44)	(2,2)
Carbofuran	16.6	222.3/165.3	222.3/123.2	40	5	16.45	(16, 20)	(2,2)
Chlorotoluron	16.6	213.2/72.0	213.2/140.1	54	5	16.20	(39,32)	(1,2)
Bendiocarb	16.7	224.2/109.1	224.2/167.3	31	5	16.48	(10,26)	(1,4)
Difenoxuron	17.0	287.1/123.2	287.1/72.1	48	5	18.27	(35, 23)	(1,2)
Fluometuron	17.06	233.2/72.1	233.2/160.2	40.7	5	16.76	(34,35)	(2,2)
Carbaryl	17.1	202.2/145.1	202.2/127.2	35	5	15.89	(13,38)	(2,2)
Atrazine	17.3	216.1/174.1	216.1/104.1	47	4	16.28	(20,40)	(2.5,2)

Metalaxyl	17.3	280.2/220.2	280.2/192.3	50	4	18.04	(21, 22)	(2,3)
Isoproturon	17.3	207.2/72.1	207.2/165.2	56	7	16.03	(33, 18)	(2,7)
Diuron	17.5	233.1/72.1	233.1/213.0	40.7	5	16.76	(34, 35)	(2,2)
Monolinuron	17.9	215.1/126.1	215.1/148.3	40	5	16.25	(18,22)	(2,2)
Ethiofencarb	17.8	226.2/107.1	226.2/164.2	28	5	16.56	(21,8)	(1.8,2)
Flazasulfuron	18.2	408.0/182.3	408.0/226.8	32	5	21.65	(30,30)	(3,4)
Metobromuron	18.5	259.0/170.1	259.0/148.2	39	5	17.48	(26,21)	(3,3)
Dimethomorph	18.5	388.2/301.2	388.2/165.2	65	5	21.01	(28,40)	(2.7,2.3)
Diphenyl sulfone	18.9	219.0/77.1	219.0/141.0	57	5	16.36	(18,45)	(2,1)
Prochloraz	19.0	376.1/308.1	376.1/266.1	40	5	20.76	(16,21)	(3.2,3)
Propazine	19.7	230.2/188.2	230.2/146.2	48	5	16.67	(31,21)	(2,3)
Cyproconazole	19.7	292.2/70.1	292.2/125.1	63	5	18.41	(49,43)	(1,2)
Chloroxuron	19.7	291.0/72.1	291.0/218.1	62	5	18.38	(40,34)	(3,2)
Methiocarb	19.9	226.2/121.2	226.2/169.2	20	5	16.56	(24,13)	(2,2)
Fenamiphos	20.1	304.2/217.0	304.2/234.2	63	5	18.74	(26,20)	(2,3)
Bromuconazole	20.1	376.0/159.2	376.0/70.0	47	5	20.76	(28,44)	(2,1)
Azoxystrobin	20.1	404.0/372.0	404.0/344.0	40	5	21.54	(20,33)	(3,3)
Terbutylazine	20.2	230.2/174.3	230.2/146.1	48	5	16.67	(23,31)	(3,2)
Cartap	20.2	238.3/175.9	238.3/172.1	36	5	16.90	(24,20)	(7,3)
Linuron	20.4	249.1/160.0	249.1/182.2	50	5	17.20	(22,19)	(3,3)
Methidathion	20.3	302.9/145.2	302.9/84.9	20	5	18.71	(13,22)	(1.3,1.8)
Promecarb	20.6	208.1/109.2	208.1/151.3	32	5	16.05	(20,14)	(3,3)
Chlorbromuron	20.9	293.1/204.1	293.1/182.2	48	5	18.43	(24,20)	(3,3)
Tebuconazole	21.1	308.2/70.0	308.2/125.2	48	4	18.86	(40,49)	(1,2)
Diflubenzuron	21.3	311.1/141.0	311.1/158.2	40	5	18.94	(40,20)	(1.5,1.8)
Malathion	22.1	331.0/127.2	331.0/285.2	43	5	19.50	(16,12)	(2,3)
Neburon	22.6	275.2/57.2	275.2/88.3	74	5	17.93	(34,22)	(2,2)
Alachlor	22.6	270.3/162.3	270.3/147.2	57	5	17.80	(26,40)	(3,3)
Metolachlor	22.7	284.3/252.3	284.3/176.3	55	5	18.19	(32,20)	(2,4)
Vinclozolin	22.7	286.1/214.0	286.1/179.0	40	7	18.24	(17,27)	(2,2)
Triflumuron	22.7	359.1/156.1	359.1/139.1	43	8	20.28	(23,46)	(2,3)
Triflumizol	22.8	346.2/278.2	346.2/73.1	30	5	19.92	(12,22)	(3,2)
Chlorfenvinphos	22.9	361.0/155.2	361.0/127.1	36	5	20.34	(18,23)	(2,2)
Difenoconazole	22.9	406.1/251.1	406.1/337.2	30	5	21.60	(33,20)	(2.8,2.8)
Dichlofluanid	23.2	333.2/123.1	333.2/224.2	38	5	19.56	(28,15)	(2,2)
Hexaflumuron	23.2	461.1/158.1	461.1/141.3	50	5	23.14	(25.7, 50)	(2,2)
Parathion	23.27	292.0/236.0	292.0/123.1	40	5	18.40	(22,40)	(3,2)
Benalaxyl	23.4	326.3/148.2	326.3/208.2	52	5	19.36	(20,29)	(2,1.6)
TPP	23.46	327.2/77.2	327.2/152.2	81	8	19.38	(53,65)	(1.9,2.2)
Triclocarban	23.6	315.0/127.0	315.0/162.0	53	5	19.05	(44,25)	(1,3)
Iprodione	24.0	330.0/245.0	330.0/101.0	50	5	19.47	(15,32)	(4,2)
Teflubenzuron	24.1	381.3/141.0	381.3/158.2	51	5	20.90	(50, 22)	(2,3)
Lufenuron	24.6	511.1/158.1	511.1/141.2	65	5	24.54	(25, 50)	(2.8,2)
Diazinon	24.7	305.3/169.3	305.3/153.0	41	5	18.77	(26, 27)	(3,2.4)
Flufenoxuron	25.2	489.1/158.1	489.1/141.1	50	5	23.92	(24, 28)	(2.5,2.5)
Buprofezin	25.7	306.4/201.2	306.4/116.2	20	5	18.81	(15, 22)	(2.5,2)
Pyriproxyfen	25.8	322.3/96.2	322.3/227.3	39	5	19.25	(23, 16)	(4,3)
Spiromesifen	28.32	371.3/273.0	371.3/255.1	20	5	20.62	(12,30)	(4,3)
Fluroxypyr	28.3	255.0/237.2	255.0/209.0	40	3	17.37	(13,24)	(4,2)

Table 2. Limits of detection (LODs) and limits of quantitation (LOQs) in olive oil

Pesticide	LOD ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Linearity equation in solvent	R^2	Linearity equation in matrix	R^2	Slope matrix/ slope standard	Signal suppression (-), enhancement (+) (%)
Cyromazine	5	10	$y = 4.96 \times 10^3x + 1.09 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 2.72 \times 10^3x + 1.6 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.55	-45.16
Thiocyclam	0.3	1	$y = 7.06 \times 10^3x - 1.46 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 7.81 \times 10^3x + 1.13 \times 10^3$	0.999	1.11	10.62
Nitempyram	1	8	$y = 446x + 2.71 \times 10^3$	0.998	$y = 518x - 2.53 \times 10^3$	0.999	1.16	16.14
Aldicarb sulfoxide	3	9	$y = 561x + 2.31 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 541x + 6.69$	1.000	0.96	-3.57
Carbendazim	0.5	1	$y = 1.08 \times 10^4x + 6.23 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 9.72 \times 10^3x + 5.52 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.90	-10.00
Thiabendazole	0.5	1.5	$y = 1.23 \times 10^4x + 3.00 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 1.25 \times 10^4x + 6.77 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.02	1.63
Monocrotophos	1	3	$y = 2.02 \times 10^3x + 9.55 \times 10^3$	0.997	$y = 2.27 \times 10^3x + 3.93 \times 10^3$	0.998	1.12	12.38
Butoxycarboxin	10	15	$y = 376x + 1.56 \times 10^3$	0.998	$y = 307x + 2.76 \times 10^3$	0.998	0.82	-18.35
Oxamyl	10	20	$y = 72.8x - 199$	0.999	$y = 72.3x + 350$	0.999	0.99	-0.69
Cambendazole	0.2	0.6	$y = 1.99 \times 10^4x - 2.86 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 1.85 \times 10^4x + 6.05 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.93	-7.04
Aldicarb sulfone	3	8	$y = 1.06 \times 10^3x + 3.91 \times 10^3$	0.998	$y = 1.15 \times 10^3x - 16.5$	1.000	1.08	8.49
Methiocarb sulfoxide	1	3.6	$y = 1.33 \times 10^4x - 6.99 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 1.08 \times 10^4x + 1.61 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.95	-18.80
Thiametoxam	2.5	5	$y = 1.66 \times 10^3x - 6.56 \times 10^3$	0.997	$y = 1.58 \times 10^3x - 2.72 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.95	-4.82
Methomyl	1	3.5	$y = 4.87 \times 10^3x + 2.69 \times 10^3$	0.997	$y = 4.02 \times 10^3x + 2.16 \times 10^4$	0.997	0.83	-17.45
Oxfendazole	0.3	0.8	$y = 2.08 \times 10^4x - 2.81 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 2.3 \times 10^4x - 6.58 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.11	10.58
Metamitron	1.2	5	$y = 5.29 \times 10^3x + 1.84 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 5.12 \times 10^3x + 6.37 \times 10^3$	0.997	0.97	3.21
Chloridazon	0.9	3	$y = 4.44 \times 10^3x - 2.31 \times 10^3$	0.998	$y = 5.09 \times 10^3x - 3.42 \times 10^3$	0.997	1.15	14.64
Imidacloprid	1	3	$y = 2.86 \times 10^3x + 6.38 \times 10^3$	0.997	$y = 2.26 \times 10^3x - 622$	0.999	0.79	-20.98
Fenuron	3.5	5.2	$y = 2.58 \times 10^3x + 6.28 \times 10^3$	0.997	$y = 2.17 \times 10^3x + 5.38 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.84	-15.89
Acetamiprid	0.1	0.3	$y = 1.00 \times 10^4x - 5.73 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 9.13 \times 10^3x + 4.88 \times 10^4$	0.998	0.91	-8.70
Dimethoate	0.1	1	$y = 3.13 \times 10^3x - 1.64 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 2.57 \times 10^3x + 9.79 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.82	-17.89
Imazalil	0.1	1.3	$y = 1.09 \times 10^4x - 9.73 \times 10^3$	0.998	$y = 1.08 \times 10^4x + 8.01 \times 10^3$	0.998	0.99	-0.92
Albendazole	0.1	0.5	$y = 5.23 \times 10^4x - 2.71 \times 10^5$	0.999	$y = 4.86 \times 10^4x + 1.21 \times 10^5$	0.999	0.93	-7.07
Methiocarb sulfone	10	18	$y = 1.66 \times 10^3x - 212$	0.999	$y = 1.75 \times 10^3x - 1.03 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.05	5.42
Mebendazole	0.1	0.4	$y = 3.31 \times 10^4x - 1.09 \times 10^5$	0.999	$y = 3.45 \times 10^4x - 2.08 \times 10^4$	1.000	1.04	4.23
Cymoxanil	6.6	20	$y = 854x - 4.71 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 678x - 1.08 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.79	-20.61
Thiacloprid	0.3	1	$y = 1.86 \times 10^4x + 5.73 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 1.99 \times 10^4x - 1.77 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.07	6.99
Butocarboxin	2.5	4	$y = 3.82 \times 10^3x + 1.34 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 3.73 \times 10^3x + 2.57 \times 10^3$	0.998	0.98	-2.36
Spiroxamine	0.05	0.3	$y = 9.7 \times 10^4x + 1.67 \times 10^5$	1.000	$y = 8.36 \times 10^4x + 5.33 \times 10^5$	0.999	0.86	-13.81
Aldicarb	2	7	$y = 1.39 \times 10^3x - 2.81 \times 10^3$	1.000	$y = 1.28 \times 10^3x + 1.48 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.92	-7.91
Oxadixyl	1	2	$y = 5.58 \times 10^3x - 1.49 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 5.92 \times 10^3x + 1.23 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.06	6.09
Bromacil	1.5	5	$y = 1.16 \times 10^3x - 502$	0.999	$y = 1.11 \times 10^3x + 4.3 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.96	-4.31
Spinosyn A	0.1	0.3	$y = 5.93 \times 10^4x - 3.11 \times 10^5$	0.998	$y = 4.51 \times 10^4x - 1.14 \times 10^5$	0.998	0.76	-23.95

Monuron	1	3.5	$y = 1.34 \times 10^4x + 4.43 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 1.58 \times 10^4x + 8.22 \times 10^3$	0.999	1.18	17.91
Lenacil	1	3.8	$y = 2.71 \times 10^3x - 1.73 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 2.9 \times 10^3x - 1.15 \times 10^4$	0.998	1.07	7.01
Simazine	0.05	0.2	$y = 2.38 \times 10^4x - 5.72 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 2.39 \times 10^4x - 3.04 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.00	0.42
Miconazole	0.1	1.2	$y = 3.77 \times 10^4x - 4.99 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 3.16 \times 10^4x + 2.1 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.84	-16.18
Spinosyn D	1.5	2.5	$y = 6.89 \times 10^3x - 1.64 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 4.52 \times 10^3x - 6.58 \times 10^3$	0.997	0.66	-34.40
Desethylterbutylazine	0.01	0.03	$y = 3.52 \times 10^4x - 1.16 \times 10^5$	0.998	$y = 3.2 \times 10^4x + 1.19 \times 10^5$	0.999	0.91	-9.09
Fenbendazole	0.1	0.4	$y = 5.79 \times 10^4x - 1.88 \times 10^5$	0.999	$y = 6.25 \times 10^4x + 2.8 \times 10^5$	0.999	1.08	7.94
Metolcarb	0.4	1.3	$y = 1.71 \times 10^4x + 7.48 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 1.71 \times 10^4x + 8.95 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.00	0.00
Pyrimethanil	0.4	1.5	$y = 9.01 \times 10^3x - 2.52 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 1.05 \times 10^4x - 2.53 \times 10^3$	0.998	1.17	16.54
Prometryn	0.05	0.3	$y = 5.5 \times 10^4x + 2.11 \times 10^5$	0.999	$y = 5.92 \times 10^4x + 4.17 \times 10^5$	0.999	1.08	7.64
Terbutrin	0.1	0.4	$y = 5.45 \times 10^4x + 2.41 \times 10^5$	0.998	$y = 5.36 \times 10^4x + 3.88 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.98	-1.65
Ethoxyquin	0.7	2.2	$y = 6.51 \times 10^3x + 1.11 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 8.84 \times 10^3x - 3.3 \times 10^3$	0.999	1.36	35.79
Carbofuran	0.07	0.6	$y = 2.3 \times 10^4x - 2.49 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 2.01 \times 10^4x + 4.63 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.87	-12.61
Chlorotoluron	0.4	1.4	$y = 1.14 \times 10^4x + 1.4 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 1.23 \times 10^4x + 1.9 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.08	7.89
Bendiocarb	1	3	$y = 2.54 \times 10^3x + 7.19 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 2.22 \times 10^3x + 1.05 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.87	-12.60
Difenoxuron	0.1	0.8	$y = 1.91 \times 10^4x - 1.57 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 1.48 \times 10^4x + 1.17 \times 10^5$	0.999	0.77	-22.51
Fluometuron	0.1	0.5	$y = 1.25 \times 10^4x - 1.86 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 9.03 \times 10^3x - 3.75 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.72	-27.76
Carbaryl	0.2	0.6	$y = 5.53 \times 10^3x - 1.61 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 5.33 \times 10^3x + 5.98 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.96	-3.62
Atrazine	0.1	0.8	$y = 6.17 \times 10^4x - 8.85 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 5.85 \times 10^4x + 1.57 \times 10^5$	0.999	0.95	-5.19
Metalaxyl	0.6	2	$y = 8.41 \times 10^3x + 414$	0.999	$y = 9.42 \times 10^3x + 1.07 \times 10^5$	0.997	1.12	12.01
Isoproturon	0.3	1	$y = 1.3 \times 10^4x - 7.45 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 1.11 \times 10^4x + 2.08 \times 10^4$	0.998	0.85	-14.62
Diuron	0.5	1.3	$y = 1.25 \times 10^4x - 1.86 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 9.03 \times 10^3x - 3.15 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.72	-27.76
Monolinuron	1	2.5	$y = 4.29 \times 10^3x - 8.76 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 3.69 \times 10^3x - 1.15 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.86	-13.99
Ethiofencarb	1	2	$y = 3.2 \times 10^3x - 289$	0.998	$y = 3.67 \times 10^3x + 9.03 \times 10^3$	0.998	1.15	14.69
Flazasulfuron	1	2.5	$y = 3.4 \times 10^4x - 7.48 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 3.22 \times 10^4x - 1.23 \times 10^5$	0.999	0.95	-5.29
Metobromuron	1	3	$y = 3.82 \times 10^3x - 2.11 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 3.50 \times 10^3x - 7.41 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.92	-8.38
Dimethomorph	0.1	0.6	$y = 1.95 \times 10^4x - 4.79 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 2.02 \times 10^4x - 4.00 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.04	3.59
Diphenyl sulfone	0.08	0.2	$y = 4.37 \times 10^3x + 8.15 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 4.88 \times 10^3x - 2.32 \times 10^3$	1.000	1.12	11.67
Prochloraz	1	2.2	$y = 5.84 \times 10^3x + 2.67 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 5.66 \times 10^3x + 3.65 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.97	-3.08
Propazine	0.04	0.15	$y = 1.02 \times 10^3x + 3.2 \times 10^3$	0.998	$y = 1.00 \times 10^3x + 9.81 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.98	-1.96
Cyproconazole	0.1	0.7	$y = 2.98 \times 10^4x + 5.63 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 2.86 \times 10^4x + 4.85 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.96	-4.03
Chloroxuron	0.1	0.25	$y = 1.95 \times 10^4x + 3.61 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 2.09 \times 10^4x + 7.07 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.07	7.18
Methiocarb	0.35	1.2	$y = 7.73 \times 10^3x - 3.8 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 7.98 \times 10^3x + 1.09 \times 10^4$	0.998	1.03	3.23
Fenamiphos	0.1	0.3	$y = 4.53 \times 10^4x + 7.63 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 4.52 \times 10^4x + 1.27 \times 10^5$	0.999	1.00	-0.22
Bromuconazole	0.3	0.5	$y = 8.43 \times 10^3x + 1.22 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 8.97 \times 10^3x + 2.24 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.06	6.41
Azoxystrobin	0.05	0.1	$y = 4.71 \times 10^4x - 7.33 \times 10^4$	0.997	$y = 4.44 \times 10^4x + 1.26 \times 10^5$	0.999	0.94	-5.73
Terbuthylazine	0.01	0.04	$y = 9.61 \times 10^4x + 1.89 \times 10^5$	0.998	$y = 1.05 \times 10^5x + 1.17 \times 10^6$	0.999	1.09	9.26
Cartap	10	20	$y = 96x + 412$	0.997	$y = 105x + 595$	0.998	1.09	9.38

Linuron	1	3.3	$y = 2.49 \times 10^3x + 6.92 \times 10^3$	0.998	$y = 2.64 \times 10^3x + 1.06 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.06	6.02
Methidathion	0.1	0.5	$y = 1.32 \times 10^4x - 2.17 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 1.34 \times 10^4x + 7.98 \times 10^3$	0.999	1.02	1.52
Promecarb	0.1	0.3	$y = 3.67 \times 10^4x + 1.61 \times 10^5$	0.999	$y = 3.32 \times 10^4x + 1.91 \times 10^5$	0.999	0.90	-9.54
Chlorbromuron	0.6	3	$y = 3.02 \times 10^3x + 1.53 \times 10^4$	0.997	$y = 3.19 \times 10^3x + 637$	0.999	1.06	5.63
Tebuconazole	0.25	1	$y = 6.67 \times 10^4x - 9.97 \times 10^3$	0.998	$y = 6.33 \times 10^4x - 1.08 \times 10^5$	0.999	0.95	-5.10
Diflubenzuron	1	3.2	$y = 3.17 \times 10^3x - 1.37 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 3.3 \times 10^3x - 2.03 \times 10^3$	0.999	1.04	4.10
Malathion	0.8	2.8	$y = 7.68 \times 10^3x - 2.1 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 5.66 \times 10^3x + 2.08 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.74	-26.30
Neburon	1	2.6	$y = 6.46 \times 10^3x + 1.79 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 6.85 \times 10^3x + 4.07 \times 10^4$	0.997	1.06	6.04
Alachlor	0.9	2.5	$y = 2.49 \times 10^3x + 1.32 \times 10^4$	0.997	$y = 2.34 \times 10^3x + 2.41 \times 10^4$	0.998	0.94	-6.02
Metolachlor	0.01	0.03	$y = 3.84 \times 10^4x + 9.01 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 3.95 \times 10^4x + 1.67 \times 10^5$	0.999	1.03	2.86
Vinclozolin	5	16.6	$y = 343x + 3.46 \times 10^3$	0.997	$y = 385x + 1.89 \times 10^3$	0.998	1.12	12.24
Triflumuron	0.5	1	$y = 9.19 \times 10^3x + 3.11 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 9.94 \times 10^3x + 3.47 \times 10^4$	0.998	1.08	8.16
Triflumizol	0.1	0.5	$y = 5.54 \times 10^4x + 2.69 \times 10^5$	0.998	$y = 5.47 \times 10^4x + 2.69 \times 10^5$	0.999	0.99	-1.26
Chlorfenvinphos	0.1	0.3	$y = 2.83 \times 10^4x + 1.3 \times 10^5$	0.997	$y = 3.32 \times 10^4x + 1.31 \times 10^5$	0.997	1.17	17.31
Difenoconazole	0.06	0.1	$y = 9.31 \times 10^4x + 3.53 \times 10^5$	0.998	$y = 9.55 \times 10^4x + 2.71 \times 10^5$	0.999	1.03	2.58
Dichlofluanid	0.5	1.8	$y = 438x - 698$	0.999	$y = 460x + 2.10 \times 10^3$	0.999	1.05	5.02
Hexaflumuron	1	5	$y = 2.75 \times 10^3x + 1.68 \times 10^4$	0.998	$y = 3.69 \times 10^3x + 9.14 \times 10^3$	0.999	1.34	34.18
Parathion	3	9	$y = 955x + 4.47 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 1.02 \times 10^3x - 300$	0.999	1.07	6.81
Benalaxyl	0.05	0.1	$y = 6.33 \times 10^4x + 3.82 \times 10^5$	0.998	$y = 6.52 \times 10^4x + 4.31 \times 10^5$	0.997	1.03	-3.00
TPP	0.06	0.1	$y = 5.76 \times 10^4x + 4.83 \times 10^5$	0.999	$y = 5.37 \times 10^4x + 5.61 \times 10^5$	0.998	0.93	-6.77
Triclocarban	0.2	0.7	$y = 6.6 \times 10^3x + 1.34 \times 10^4$	0.999	$y = 6.54 \times 10^3x + 1.63 \times 10^4$	0.999	0.99	-0.91
Iprodione	5	16	$y = 427x + 591$	0.997	$y = 407x + 963$	0.999	0.95	-4.68
Teflubenzuron	1	3.7	$y = 1.15 \times 10^3x - 1.17 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 981x + 3.56 \times 10^3$	0.999	0.85	-14.70
Lufenuron	5	18	$y = 884x + 4.49 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 959x + 9.48 \times 10^3$	0.997	1.08	8.48
Diazinon	0.03	0.1	$y = 3.95 \times 10^5x + 2.82 \times 10^6$	0.997	$y = 4.28 \times 10^5x + 3.48 \times 10^6$	0.997	1.08	8.35
Flufenoxuron	0.8	2.6	$y = 6.86 \times 10^3x + 4.51 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 8.12 \times 10^3x + 1.24 \times 10^4$	0.999	1.18	18.37
Buprofezin	0.05	0.3	$y = 1.22 \times 10^5x + 7.16 \times 10^5$	0.997	$y = 1.31 \times 10^5x + 7.8 \times 10^5$	0.997	1.07	7.38
Pyriproxyfen	0.01	0.05	$y = 2.24 \times 10^5x + 1.03 \times 10^6$	0.998	$y = 2.38 \times 10^5x + 7.95 \times 10^5$	0.999	1.06	6.25
Spiromesifen	0.5	1.4	$y = 1.53 \times 10^4x + 7.73 \times 10^4$	0.997	$y = 1.77 \times 10^4x + 1.31 \times 10^5$	0.997	1.16	15.69
Fluroxypyr	5	10	$y = 408x + 8.44 \times 10^3$	0.999	$y = 399x + 3.8 \times 10^4$	1.000	0.98	-2.21

Table 3. MRM ratios in solvent and matrix, CV% within the range of concentration from LOQ up to 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, and the difference between the MRM ratios in solvent and in matrix

Pesticide	MRM ratio in solvent (mean value, LOQ to 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	CV%	MRM ratio in matrix (mean value, LOQs to 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	CV%	Difference between MRM ratios in solvent and in matrix (%)	Difference between CVs for solvent and for matrix
Cyromazine	1.29	20.5	1.12	20.8	13.18	-0.3
Thiocyclam	1.84	19.7	1.7	26	7.61	-6.3
Nitempyram	1.97	4.5	2	18.9	-1.52	-14.4
Aldicarb sulfoxide	4.79	19.4	5.16	17.9	-7.72	1.5
Carbendazim	2.83	22.3	3.21	17	-13.43	5.3
Thiabendazole	1.2	19.8	1.2	18.4	0.00	1.4
Monocrotophos	1.53	19.4	1.37	16.5	10.46	2.9
Butoxyacboxin	1.54	22	1.7	20.9	-10.39	1.1
Oxamyl	5.34	24.9	5.9	23.5	-10.49	1.4
Cambendazole	1.18	12.8	1.35	25.2	-14.41	-12.4
Aldicarb sulfone	1.21	12.1	1.36	19.2	-12.40	-7.1
Methiocarb sulfoxide	3.7	20.7	3.55	19.2	4.05	1.5
Thiametoxam	1.23	11.3	1.2	22.7	2.44	-11.4
Methomyl	1.51	21.3	1.53	27.3	-1.32	-6
Oxfendazole	1.95	14.6	1.97	26.2	-1.03	-11.6
Metamitron	3.73	19	3.7	20.5	0.80	-1.5
Chloridazon	1.49	22.4	1.52	19.8	-2.01	2.6
Imidacloprid	1.46	21.9	1.4	14.2	4.11	7.7
Fenuron	3.77	22.2	3.29	17.9	12.73	4.3
Acetamiprid	4.49	10.8	5	22.6	-11.36	-11.8
Dimethoate	1.51	20.4	1.34	18.7	11.26	1.7
Imazalil	3.48	9.9	3.81	16.4	-9.48	-6.5
Albendazole	1.92	20.2	2.21	22.9	-15.10	-2.7
Methiocarb sulfone	2.71	19.1	3.12	18.3	-15.13	0.8
Mebendazole	2.67	27.1	2.89	15.6	-8.24	11.5
Cymoxanil	1.45	21.3	1.43	21.5	1.38	-0.2
Thiacloprid	6.16	19.1	5.8	25.6	5.84	-6.5
Butocarboxin	5.28	23.5	5.15	25.1	2.46	-1.6
Spiroxamine	1.78	25.5	1.6	25.6	10.11	-0.1
Aldicarb	1.27	7.1	1.48	25.1	-16.54	-18
Oxadixyl	5.97	23.6	6.18	25.7	-3.52	-2.1
Bromacil	4.96	13.9	4.2	14.9	15.32	-1
Spinosyn A	27.7	18.6	25.3	8.5	8.66	10.1
Monuron	5.73	17	4.98	6.5	13.09	10.5
Lenacil	4.89	18	5.38	29.4	-10.02	-11.4
Simazine	1.12	3.3	1.2	18.4	-7.14	-15.1
Miconazole	30.7	23	26.4	15.8	14.01	7.2
Spinosyn D	21.5	16.9	23.6	22.6	-9.77	-5.7
Desethylterbutylazine	3.63	13.1	3.5	25.1	3.58	-12
Fenbendazole	1.36	18.8	1.3	22	4.41	-3.2
Metolcarb	2.88	13.8	3.1	15.8	-7.64	-2
Pyrimethanil	1.54	11.2	1.29	17	16.23	-5.8
Prometryn	1.4	15.8	1.5	22.1	-7.14	-6.3
Terbutrin	6.33	25.7	6.49	27.9	-2.53	-2.2
Ethoxyquin	1.43	24	1.6	17	-11.89	7
Carbofuran	1.28	15.7	1.2	15.5	6.25	0.2
Chlorotoluron	12	12.9	12.5	25.2	-4.17	-12.3
Bendiocarb	3.85	24.8	4.2	20.4	-9.09	4.4
Difenoxuron	1.33	19.8	1.3	9.3	2.26	10.5
Fluometuron	14.6	19.7	14.38	8.8	1.51	10.9
Carbaryl	1.75	6.6	1.83	13.9	-4.57	-7.3
Atrazine	2.83	11.3	3.16	19	-11.66	-7.7

Metalaxyl	1.06	23.3	1.11	23.4	-4.72	-0.1
Isoproturon	4.92	18	4.27	16.3	13.21	1.7
Diuron	72	22.1	64.4	36.3	10.56	-14.2
Monolinuron	1.27	21.2	1.23	22.6	3.15	-1.4
Ethiofencarb	1.45	18.5	1.57	19.8	-8.28	-1.3
Flazasulfuron	11.7	16.3	10.8	19.1	7.69	-2.8
Metobromuron	1.36	23.8	1.43	22.8	-5.15	1
Dimethomorph	2.32	15.1	2.39	13.5	-3.02	1.6
Diphenyl sulfone	2.31	21.5	2.06	19.8	10.82	1.7
Prochloraz	5.13	9.3	5.15	18.8	-0.39	-9.5
Propazine	1.35	17.8	1.17	22.5	13.33	-4.7
Cyproconazole	1.44	15.2	1.34	12.1	6.94	3.1
Chloroxuron	13.2	23.6	14.1	17.8	-6.82	5.8
Methiocarb	1.4	22.4	1.53	20.8	-9.29	1.6
Fenamiphos	1.84	20.2	1.85	16.8	-0.54	3.4
Bromuconazole	6.82	20.8	7.45	12.4	-9.24	8.4
Azoxystrobin	3.05	14.7	3.6	14	-18.03	0.7
Terbuthylazine	1.32	14.5	1.4	16.9	-6.06	-2.4
Cartap	1.22	20.4	1.24	21.7	-1.64	-1.3
Linuron	1.46	23.5	1.44	16.5	1.37	7
Methidathion	1.88	18.9	1.61	23.7	14.36	-4.8
Promecarb	1.35	19.9	1.15	18.9	14.81	1
Chlorbromuron	1.52	18.7	1.3	11.4	14.47	7.3
Tebuconazole	4.38	17.8	4.67	20.4	-6.62	-2.6
Diflubenzuron	1.15	6.2	1.14	28.5	0.87	-22.3
Malathion	2.19	21.8	2.17	20.9	0.91	0.9
Neburon	1.05	18.1	1.21	12.2	-15.24	5.9
Alachlor	2.66	15.2	2.74	20.8	-3.01	-5.6
Metolachlor	3.28	14.2	3.33	25.4	-1.52	-11.2
Vinclozolin	31.2	20.4	29.2	20.6	6.41	-0.2
Triflumuron	1.76	12	1.78	17.1	-1.14	-5.1
Triflumizol	5.51	14.5	4.46	14.1	19.06	0.4
Chlorfenvinphos	1.95	8.5	1.95	10.3	0.00	-1.8
Difenoconazole	6.61	16.1	7.72	20.2	-16.79	-4.1
Dichlofluanid	1.36	14.8	1.17	11.5	13.97	3.3
Hexaflumuron	1.92	4.7	2.13	12	-10.94	-7.3
Parathion	1.2	29.9	1.21	18.1	-0.83	11.8
Benalaxyl	1.47	5.7	1.45	4.9	1.36	0.8
TPP	1.31	6.8	1.22	11.5	6.87	-4.7
Triclocarban	1.42	4.7	1.4	8.9	1.41	-4.2
Iprodione	1.4	25.7	1.37	24.1	2.14	1.6
Teflubenzuron	1.11	9.6	1.07	16.9	3.60	-7.3
Lufenuron	1.67	17.5	1.89	11.7	-13.17	5.8
Diazinon	1.52	10.3	1.49	7.5	1.97	2.8
Flufenoxuron	10.7	2.9	10.2	18.9	4.67	-16
Buprofezin	1.62	19.2	1.6	18.9	1.23	0.3
Pyriproxyfen	4.42	5.5	4.6	7.3	-4.07	-1.8
Spiromesifen	3.74	8.5	3.6	10.4	3.74	-1.9
Fluroxypyr	1.17	9.5	1.26	20.5	-7.69	-11
